

A. Medicine and Health

December 18, 2020 (Science)

People with Down syndrome face high risk from coronavirus

Meredith Wadman

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.370.6523.1384>

The author summarizes the available data on the clinical severity and outcome of COVID-19 in patients with Down Syndrome, emphasizing the need for those with trisomy 21 to be prioritized for vaccination.

December 17, 2020 (NEJM)

REGN-COV2, a Neutralizing Antibody Cocktail, in Outpatients with Covid-19

David M. Weinreich, Sumathi Sivapalasingam, Thomas Norton et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2035002>

An anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibody cocktail was given to patients within 3 days after diagnosis of COVID-19 by PCR. In patients who were antibody negative at baseline, treatment was associated with rapid viral clearance and potentially with a less frequent need for medical attention. The effect was less marked among patients who were antibody-positive at baseline.

December 17, 2020 (JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.)

Early Outcomes From Early Tracheostomy for Patients With COVID-19.

Kwak PE, Connors JR, Benedict PA, et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoto.2020.4837>

This cohort study assesses outcomes from early tracheostomy in the airway management of patients with COVID-19 requiring mechanical ventilation. The authors find that timing of tracheostomy was significantly associated with length of stay, suggesting that in patients with COVID-19, early tracheostomy was noninferior to late tracheostomy and may be associated with improvement in some outcomes

December 16, 2020 (Radiology: Artificial Intelligence)

Combining Initial Radiographs and Clinical Variables Improves Deep Learning Prognostication of Patients with COVID-19 from the Emergency Department

Young Joon (Fred) Kwon, Danielle Toussie, Mark Finkelstein et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1148/ryai.2020200098>

In this retrospective cohort study, the authors aimed to train a deep learning classification algorithm to predict chest radiography severity scores and clinical outcomes in patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).

Chest Xrays of COVID-19 positive patients were examined for opacities and assigned a clinically validated severity score. Models were trained on the CXR severity score, on clinical variables and on both together. The authors found that the combination of imaging and clinical information improves outcome predictions.

December 15, 2020 (BMJ Nutrition, Prevention & Health)

Global, regional, and national estimates of target population sizes for COVID-19 vaccination: descriptive study

Wei Wang, Qianhui Wu, Juan Yang et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m4704>

This descriptive study aims to provide global, regional, and national estimates of target population sizes for COVID-19 vaccination to inform country specific immunisation strategies on a global scale. The distribution of target groups at country and regional levels highlights the importance of designing an equitable and efficient plan for vaccine prioritisation and allocation. Each country should evaluate different strategies and allocation schemes based on local epidemiology, underlying population health, projections of available vaccine doses, and preference for vaccination strategies that favour direct or indirect benefits

B. Science and Engineering

December 31, 2020 (Scientific Reports)

A model to rate strategies for managing disease due to COVID-19 infection

Shiyan Wang & Doraiswami Ramkrishna

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-79817-7>

The authors demonstrate that when machine learning is employed together with the mechanistic framework of a mathematical model, there can be a considerably enhanced understanding of complex systems. A mathematical model describing the viral infection dynamics reveals two transmissibility parameters influenced by the management strategies in the area for the control of the current pandemic. Treatment of population data with the model shows that restricted non-essential business closure, school closing and strictures on mass gathering influence the spread of infection.

December 30, 2020 (Scientific Reports)

Rapid and complete inactivation of SARS-CoV-2 by ultraviolet-C irradiation

Nadia Storm, Lindsay G. A. McKay, Sierra N. Downs et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-79600-8>

In this paper, the researchers describe the inactivation of SARS-CoV-2 in both wet and dry format using ultraviolet (UV)-C light source at 254 nm. They show

that for contaminated surfaces, only seconds of exposure is required for complete inactivation, allowing for easy implementation in decontamination workflows.

December 17, 2020 (Environmental Research)

Did anomalous atmospheric circulation favor the spread of COVID-19 in Europe?

A. Sanchez-Lorenzo, J. Vaquero-Martínez, J. Calbó et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110626>

In this study the authors show that an unusual persistent anticyclonic situation prevailing in southwestern Europe during February 2020 could have resulted in favorable conditions. It seems possible that the strong atmospheric stability and associated dry conditions that dominated in these regions may have favored the virus propagation by short-range droplet and aerosol (airborne) transmission, or/and by changing social contact patterns. Subsequent atmospheric circulation conditions in Europe (July 2020) and the U.S. (October 2020) seem to support their hypothesis.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

December 24, 2020 (Journal of Business Research)

The effect of political ideology and message frame on donation intent during the COVID-19 pandemic

Patrick Van Esch, Yuanyuan (Gina) Cui, Shailendra Pratap Jain.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.12.040>

This paper investigates COVID-19 related consumers' donation intent predicated on their political ideology and the message frame - one emphasizing the statistical number of affected victims, and the other focusing on a specifically identified victim. Rather unsurprisingly, from three studies, it is found that the impact of the message frame depends on consumers' political ideology. "Politically conservative" consumers respond to the identifiable victim (vs. statistical victims) frame more favourably, while "politically liberal" consumers are indifferent across the two frames (Studies 1 and 2). The paper concludes with some implications for practice.

December 15, 2020 (Contemporary Education Dialogue)

Teachers' Voices on the Impact of COVID-19 on School Education: Are Ed-Tech Companies Really the Panacea?

Samta Jain, Marie Lall & Anviti Singh.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0973184920976433>

This article presents the voices of teachers affected by the pandemic in India and critically examines the role of Ed-Tech companies, which pertain to fill the online teaching gap. Between 29 April 2020, and 29 May 2020, an online survey was administered to 550 Delhi and National Capital Region (NCR)

teachers, of which 288 responded. The data show that the inequalities between private schools and government schools are sharpened by the move to online education. This is compounded by the fact that students from economically weaker sections of society have become hard to reach, and teachers do not know how to support hard-to-reach students who are also severely affected by the pandemic. The paper notes that so-called “Ed-Tech companies” have been presenting themselves as a panacea to this problem. However, the authors conclude that Ed-Tech solutions are not relevant for hard-to-reach students or teachers in schools that serve hard-to-reach communities.